

Informative

COVID-19: REMEDY IS BETTER THAN CURE

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Abstract- Some crucial points to get recover more rapidly and safely from COVID-19. Here we will express our study based on some critical points from which how a positive patient gets rid of COVID-19. Where all doctors and scientists apply their best methods to treat the patients we are also supposed to put forward our few valuable points regards to treat the patients, and when we see in our daily life that we apply these methods in our life to get rid of from different diseases and we have to get better results from these critical points. So, it is better to apply these critical points to the patients, and we all mostly aim that this method will work out in this field. Although these critical points do not have any non-benefit from our aspects.

Keywords- COVID-19, steam treatment, improve circulation.

Key points are as given below

- a. Steam therapy is not a new concept. The ancient Egyptians knew the benefits of inhalation therapy and built public toilets. Even today, experts recommended steam therapy to treat many health problems, especially those related to the respiratory systems.
- b. Steam is the most widely used hydrotherapy treatment. The history of the steam bath starts with naturopathy, a medical system in which water is the main contributor to health, especially as preventive. Use of steam two times in a day.

I. BENEFITS

A. Easy breathing

- a. Whether it is sinus congestion, common cold, flu, bronchitis, sinusitis, asthma, allergies, or a respiratory infection, steam is very beneficial.
- b. Vapor inhalation involves introducing hot, moist air into the lungs through the nose and throat, which in turn helps to open the breasts to facilitate breathing.
- c. Inhalation of vapor helps release the pressure that builds up in your sinuses and prevents mucus's proper secretion. It also smooths your mucus membranes and helps clear the congestion in your nose. This, in turn, helps reduce a headache.
- d. Whenever we inhale steam from our nose, it gets to pass through the nose and reaches the air sacs of the lungs where they can increase the inner volume of air sacs, increasing the area for more air to come into the lungs and help to get breath quickly.

B. Improves Circulation

Sitting in a steam room is very beneficial for elder people as it has good effects on the cardiovascular system.

A study was conducted in 2012 which states that moist heat which is provided by the steam room improves circulation by expanding (dilating) the small blood vessels or capillaries. Due to the dilated vessels, blood can easily flow and transport oxygen to the whole body.

Another advantage of the steam room is that it reduces blood pressure and keeps the heart healthier.

C. Treat the headache

Inhalation of vapor helps to release the pressure that's build up in your sinuses and prevents the proper secretion of mucus. It also smoothens your mucus membranes and helps clear the congestion in your nose. Thus, in turn, helps reduce a headache.

D. Reduce stress

- a. The steam bath's hot heat helps the body release endorphins, a chemical that feels good and helps a lot in reducing the effects of stress; also, endorphins help you enjoy a night of deep sleep.
- b. Besides that, the heat of the steam increases the blood circulation to relax the muscles.
- c. Besides, the heat of the steam room opens the airways, which improves breathing. A suitable respirator helps relax the mind and body.
- d. Another advantage of the heat of the steam room is that it makes the body release endorphins which is known as "good feel" hormones because they help to reduce the feeling of stress.
- e. A steam room also helps to decrease the cortisol level. Cortisol is a hormone that responds to stress in the body. When cortisol level decreases people feel more relaxed and happier.

E. Expel toxins

An accumulation of toxins and impurities in the body can affect their immunity and lead to different health problems. F. Steam dilates (expand) blood vessels, due to dilated vessels blood circulation improves, and more oxygen is supplied to the muscles.

II. CONCLUSION

- a. Drink hot milk four times a day.
- b. Drink hot tea four times a day.
- c. Drink hot soup four times a day.
- d. Use liquid forms of food.
- e. Always use hot food to eat.

These all are should maintain the body temperature warm for a whole day which favors unhabitual environment for the virus to play their role in our body, as virus unable to grow in this environment so our body B&T-cells starts producing immunity against that virus, and all these items also provide better nutrition to our body which should be essential.

Also due to these things to be used in our daily diet, it makes our nose pipe warm at all time so that when the bit amount of virus enters in our nose pipe so it will kill itself due to the warm temperature of our nose it's the first line of defense which should play their role whenever it happens.

III. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First and foremost, praises and thanks to God, the Almighty, for His showers of blessings throughout my research work to complete the research successfully.

I would like to express my deep and sincere gratitude to my research supervisor, Dr. Kumud Pant. Ph.D., Professor, Graphic Era Deemed to be University, Dehradun, Uttarakhand for allowing me to do research and providing invaluable guidance throughout this research. Her dynamism, vision, sincerity, and motivation have deeply inspired me. She has taught me the methodology to carry out the research and to present the research works as clearly as possible. It was a great privilege and honor to work and study under her guidance. I am extremely grateful for what she has offered me. I would also like to thank him for her friendship, empathy, and a great sense of humor

I am extremely grateful to my parents for their love, prayers, caring and sacrifices for educating and preparing me for my future. I am very much thankful to my parents for their love, understanding, prayers, and continuing support to complete this research work.

IV. REFERENCE

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